

THE IMPACT OF WORLD WAR II ON THE SURKHANDARYA OASIS.

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Annotation: *This article briefly describes the beginning of the Second World War, which caused great losses to the world population, and its impact on the people of the Surkhandarya oasis of the Uzbek SSR, albeit far from the battlefields, the courageous actions and courage of the Surkhandarya people.*

Keywords: *"Pattakesar", "Dushanbe-Karatag", "Pravda", "Houdak", "Zolotprommat".*

The outbreak of the war on June 22, 1941, shook the hearts of all the peoples living in the former USSR, and the people set out to fight the scourge of fascism. The cold news of the war reached Uzbekistan, which was part of the USSR, including the people of Surkhandarya region. The beginning of the war also touched the hearts of the people living in the Surkhandarya oasis, arousing anger and hatred for fascism.

The war ushered in a period of peaceful coexistence and work, the task of which was to organize the defense of the country, to live and work in accordance with the requirements of the military age, and, if necessary, to give our lives for freedom, peace and tranquility. Every opportunity had to be spent on winning the war, which required hard work, relentless struggle, irreparable losses, strong will, high responsibility, strong patience and courage. [1] From the very first days of the war, rallies were held among the workers of the oasis to condemn the war, to declare their constant readiness for war against fascism, and at the same time to call for a victory over fascism. Such rallies began to be held in every enterprise and organization, collective farm and state farms, mahallas, educational institutions of the region.

On July 22, 1941, the day the news of the Cold War broke out, a rally of thousands of kolkhoz members of the Pattakesar village council in Termez district took place. At the rally, they accepted the appeal: "If necessary, we will turn our ketmons into rifles, and will not allow the dark forces to put their beaks on our beautiful policemen." At the anti-fascist rally on June 23, workers at the Houdak oil

field adopted a statement saying, "From this day forward, we consider ourselves mobilized." [2]

Such demonstrations took place in Voroshilov Oil Trust, Termez Zolotprommat Cooperative, Termez Cotton Ginning Plant, Jarkurgan Mehnat Rohat collective farm, Sherabad MTS, Shurchi village councils and every production enterprise in the region. lib passed. In these demonstrations, the peace-loving people of Surkhandarya began to make decisions, cursing the galas of fascism that ignited the flames of war, and expressing their readiness to do everything possible to escape the scourge of fascism and, if necessary, to sacrifice their lives for peace and freedom of future generations. They worked diligently in an attempt to achieve new heights in production in response to the onslaught of fascism.

For example, on the day of the news of the war, Yu. and on the same day excavated 50 cubic meters of land instead of 7 cubic meters.

With the outbreak of the war, the call for new labor victories intensified in the region, and new achievements began to be made in the field of production. But victory could not be achieved only by working behind the scenes, by crushing the hated head of the enemy in his own nest, who gave his life in battles and ignited the flames of war, who threatened the peace of the peoples of the world. Every Surkhandarya Aryan who felt the demands of this military age understood that he had been mobilized from the day the war began. Hundreds of heroes, who considered themselves responsible for the peace of the peoples, the well-being of the people and the bright life of the next generation, began to appeal to the military commissariats to send them to the front. [3]

In particular, Mikhail Sakisovich Dalniyans, an agronomist living in Termez, wrote in a telegram to IV Stalin, chairman of the State Defense Committee: If you allow me to go to the front, I will not spare all my blood, not only my blood, but also my life for peace. " in a written application to the military commissariat asking, "I know how to drive a machine, I can work in a car. I have my parents and wife at home. They are all able to work. I'd like you to send me to the front. I swear that I will justify the trust and beat the Nazis mercilessly. " Koserev, Kravchuk, Kichine, members of the Termez Rodina artel, Muhammadiev from Sherabad, Islamov from Shur, and Normuradov from Zharkurgan also filed similar applications. [4]

The outbreak of the war had fueled the hatred of fascism in the hearts of teenagers as well as all adults. On July 3, 1941, the chairman of the State Defense Committee, I. V. Stalin, addressed the people on the radio. After hearing this speech, teenagers such as V. Buryan, Juma Normammedov, Mirabdullaev, Medvedov, who were resting in the pioneer camp of Termez district, applied to be sent to the front.

F. Knyazev, a student of School No. 10 in Termez, also wrote a letter to the city military commissariat asking to be sent to the front. I am very interested in knowing the tank and managing it. I ask the conscription commission to make me achieve this dream," wrote Akanin, a graduate of the Marx School in Moscow. was.

During the bloody battles against the scourge of fascism, both men and women felt responsible for the fight against fascism and began to appeal to the military commissariats to send them to the front. In particular, F. Khakimov, a teacher at the Pravda newspaper in Termez, applied to the city military commissariat to be admitted to the sanitary detachment of the active army. Dozens of women, such as Tillo Fayzieva from Sherabad, Vera Vyalochkina from Termez, Anna Shumikhina, and Al Fomina, are also mentioned in military-historical chronicles.

In all, more than 2,000 applications were received by military commissariats across the province at the beginning of the war, asking them to mobilize themselves on the front. In June-July 1941, 20,000 people volunteered to go to the front. Parents, who were watching their light battles in battle, and women, who were watching their spouses at the front, began to give the warriors the task of brutally destroying the enemy. Shamirbobo Mirzaev, a member of the Red Border collective farm in Termez district, accompanied his son to the army and said: "My son, be brave, fight bravely. I will do my best to take your place here and turn my collective farm into an impregnable fortress."

In connection with the beginning of the war, the mobilization of the male population, engaged in creative work in various sectors of the regional economy, to the front, also created unfavorable conditions in the regional economy. Women, children and the elderly are responsible for all local production. They worked tirelessly in factories and mills, driving tractors, working between rows of cotton, tending livestock, and preparing warm clothes and food for warriors. [6]

The mobilization of able-bodied men in the province has created a shortage of specialists in the province's economy. Allowing delays in the manufacturing sector or shutting down existing enterprises was a convenient opportunity for the enemy and could have delayed the minutes of victory somewhat. Taking into account this situation, the workers of the Surkhandarya oasis, in accordance with the requirements of the military situation, worked valiantly in the fields of industrial enterprises and collective farms instead of their comrades who went to war.

In general, the war subjected the whole sphere and everyone to the requirements of the military age, and, of course, the people of the region faced enormous difficulties in achieving this. However, these challenges were overcome through the people's great zeal, perseverance and confidence in the bright days.

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